

Madani: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin
Volume 2, Nomor 7, Juli 2024, Halaman 613-618
Licensed by CC BY-SA 4.0
E-ISSN: 2986-6340
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12771700>

Enriching Students' Vocabulary through Kahoot

Siti Asriani Amuati¹, Sri Agriyanti Mestari¹, Helena Badu^{1*}

¹English Language Education Program, Universitas Negeri Gorontalo

*Email korespondensi: helenabadu@ung.ac.id

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine whether the use of the game Kahoot can enrich students' English vocabulary. The method used in this research is a quantitative pre-experimental design. The sample in this study consisted of 19 students from Class VII B of SMP N 7 Gorontalo. The researcher collected pre-test and post-test scores for data analysis, then calculated the mean scores and percentage scores. The mean score of the students in the pre-test was 57.3, while the mean score of the students in the post-test was 72.2. Therefore, it can be concluded that the game Kahoot can improve and further enrich students' English vocabulary. The results of this research show that the working hypothesis (Ha) is accepted and the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected.

Kata kunci: vocabulary, media, kahoot

Abstrak

Tujuan dari penelitian ini adalah untuk menentukan apakah penggunaan permainan Kahoot dapat memperkaya kosakata bahasa Inggris siswa. Metode yang digunakan dalam penelitian ini adalah desain pra-eksperimental kuantitatif. Sampel dalam penelitian ini terdiri dari 19 siswa dari kelas VII B SMP N 7 Gorontalo. Peneliti mengumpulkan skor pre-test dan post-test untuk analisis data, kemudian menghitung skor rata-rata dan persentase skor. Skor rata-rata siswa pada pre-test adalah 57,3, sedangkan skor rata-rata siswa pada post-test adalah 72,2. Oleh karena itu, dapat disimpulkan bahwa permainan Kahoot dapat meningkatkan dan lebih memperkaya kosakata bahasa Inggris siswa. Hasil penelitian ini menunjukkan bahwa hipotesis kerja (Ha) diterima dan hipotesis nol (Ho) ditolak.

Kata kunci: kosakata, media, kahoot

Article Info

Received date: 7 Juli 2024

Revised date: 12 Juli 2024

Accepted date: 17 Juli 2024

INTRODUCTION

English has become the most important language for communication in the globalized world. As we know, almost all aspects of our lives involve English, especially in terms of communication. Therefore, mastering English is essential for effective communication. To support the mastery of English skills, learning vocabulary is fundamental, as it forms the basis of communication.

Those with a limited vocabulary will struggle to communicate effectively. This aligns with Thornbury (2002), learning additional vocabulary will greatly enhance our English proficiency. With grammar, we can express very little, but with words, we can convey nearly everything. Flohr (2010) also argues that vocabulary is important for students to learn because without it, they wouldn't be able to convey their thoughts and communicate in a way that other students or native English speakers probably understand. In conclusion, learning vocabulary is vital. Without it, we cannot interact or express our ideas effectively when meeting other people or native English speakers.

However, many people, especially students, still struggle with learning English. This is similar to the experiences researchers had during PPL activities, where they found that many students did not understand English lessons due to a limited vocabulary. For example, when researchers asked

questions about assignments, many students had difficulty answering because they did not know enough English vocabulary. This issue can be attributed to several factors, one of the most common being the lack of vocabulary mastered by students, making it difficult for them to use English. Therefore, one effective effort to enrich students' vocabulary is to teach them using a relaxed and fun method, such as through games.

Games are an effective medium for enriching and improving students' vocabulary. There are many games that can help students remember and expand their vocabulary easily. To assist students in learning vocabulary, the researcher used the game Kahoot because it is relevant to current trends. During the pandemic, many educators transitioned to online learning, and this approach continues to be popular even now, after the pandemic has ended.

Kahoot is an instructional technology used in schools and other educational institutions, designed as a game-based learning platform. Users can access this game directly through a web browser or app. Kahoot can be played in class with students. This is in accordance with Bicen & Kocakoyun (2018) that Kahoot is an application with multiple choice questions that any student can play. Brand and Brooker in Al-Manar (2019) also stated that teachers and students can use the game-based learning platform Kahoot for free. With this game, we may play, learn, have fun, and celebrate. Therefore, Kahoot has been chosen for this study because it is also a learning tool. Licorish et al. (2017) also stated that Kahoot makes students more participating and active, and enables learners to argue for the decisions they have made which are the most desired for them. In other words, the Kahoot game may be employed as another way to inject some fun into the classroom environment while teaching vocabulary in English.

METHOD

In this research, the researcher used quantitative pre-experimental research methods. According to Sugiyono (2015) pre-experimental research is a study in which the mean score from the pre-test and post-tests is compared to determine whether or not the variable under study had an effect. This is accomplished by administering a pre-test before the treatment and a post-test afterward. The design used is a one-group pre-test and post-test design. This study uses an initial test rather than a comparison class to determine the impact of using Kahoot on learning and whether the variable under study had an effect. The population of this research consists of all VII grade students at SMP Negeri 7 Gorontalo, with the sample being the 19 students in class VII B.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Findings of the students' vocabulary achievement

1. Pre-test; the following is the table of pre-test score

Table 1. Scores of Pre-test

No	Respondents	Score
1	R1	84
2	R2	81
3	R3	81
4	R4	81
5	R5	65
6	R6	62
7	R7	60
8	R8	59
9	R9	57
10	R10	57
11	R11	54
12	R12	54
13	R13	54
14	R14	54
15	R15	51
16	R16	46

No	Respondents	Score
17	R17	32
18	R18	30
19	R19	27
	Mean	57,3

Based on the pre-test results, the researcher first determined the mean score:

$$M_x = \sum x/N$$

$$M_x = 1089/19$$

$$M_x = 57,3$$

Additionally, the researcher calculated the percentage of students who achieved the passing score (KKM) using the following formula:

$$P = f/N \times 100\%$$

$$P = 10/19 \times 100\%$$

$$P = 53\%$$

Based on these results, the mean pre-test score was 57.3. Nine students scored below the KKM, while 10 students achieved scores above it. From this study, it can be inferred that more than half of the VII grade students at SMP Negeri 7 Gorontalo still have insufficient vocabulary knowledge.

2. Treatment

Researchers implemented a treatment for students by using the game-based learning platform Kahoot. Each session starts with an introduction to the material, specifically descriptive text, and concludes with practice questions using Kahoot.

3. Post-test; the following is the table of post-test score

Table 2. Scores of Pre-test

No	Respondents	Score
1	R1	84
2	R2	81
3	R3	86
4	R4	89
5	R5	86
6	R6	73
7	R7	86
8	R8	59
9	R9	81
10	R10	73
11	R11	86
12	R12	57
13	R13	81
14	R14	62
15	R15	57
16	R16	73
17	R17	81
18	R18	51
19	R19	73
	Mean	72.2

Based on the post-test results, the researcher first determined mean score:

$$M_x = \sum x/N$$

$$M_x = 1372/19$$

$$M_x = 72.2$$

Furthermore, the researcher calculated the percentage of students who achieved the passing score (KKM) using the following formula:

$$P = f/N \times 100\%$$

$$P = 14/19 \times 100\%$$

$$P = 74\%$$

The mean post-test score is 72.2, based on the results shown above. Fourteen students, or 70.5%, met the minimum competency criteria (KKM), while five students scored below the criteria. This indicates an improvement in the mean student score from pre-test to post-test. The pre-test mean was 53%, while the post-test mean increased to 74%. The data is presented in the table below:

Table 1. The Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test

No	Test	Students' Score		Mean	Percentage
		Lowest	Highest		
1	Pre-Test	27	84	57,3	53 %
2	Post-Test	51	89	72.2	74 %

The diagram also illustrates the comparison. The percentage of students who passed the KKM is shown below:

Image 1. Diagram of Pre-test

Image 2. Diagram of Post-test

Based on the diagram above, there was a significant increase in the percentage of students who passed the criteria. In the pre-test, only 10 students met the criteria, while 9 students did not. However, in the post-test, there was substantial progress. Fourteen students met the criteria, while only 5 students did not reach the predetermined assessment standards. It can be concluded that the post-test was successful, as many students exceeded the specified criteria, with 74% of the total students in the class passing.

It can be concluded that using Kahoot can enrich students' vocabulary. Students are interested in playing this game because the application is comprehensive and offers many features; true or false, multiple choice; guess the picture, then fill in the 4 blank parts. This is in accordance with Dellos (2015) that Kahoot is a game-based learning platform that aims to be a responsive system for students, providing a way that makes students interested in using it in vocabulary learning. From

this explanation, it can be concluded that Kahoot has a positive impact on students, encouraging them to participate more actively in class and motivating them to learn English, especially vocabulary.

Researchers analyzed the collected data to answer the research questions in this study. The pre-test results revealed that many students still struggled with vocabulary, as evidenced by their random answers on the KD 3.7 descriptive text material. Recognizing that the vocabulary issues faced by junior high school students could be addressed, researchers implemented the Kahoot learning media to help students learn vocabulary easily and comfortably. The goal was to resolve these issues through engaging and effective game-based learning.

In this study, the implementation of Kahoot proved successful. Students were enthusiastic and actively participated in class, enjoying the learning process without feeling pressured. The competitive element of the game encouraged students to learn more, as they felt challenged to outperform their peers. As noted by Kadarwati et al. (2021), using Kahoot with personal accounts excited students to achieve the highest scores and answer quickly, with the top participants' names displayed on the screen. This served as an indirect reward, motivating students to excel. In summary, Kahoot effectively increased students' vocabulary and engagement, making the learning experience enjoyable and productive.

During the research, the classroom atmosphere was relaxed, fun, and engaging. Typically, students can become bored with traditional book-based learning or simple teacher explanations. However, it was evident from the students' expressions and body language that they were more enthusiastic and active when the Kahoot game media was used. Students who previously appeared lazy and disinterested became more lively and eager to participate in the learning process. This finding is in accordance with what Khoshsima et al. (2015) stated that games can be an alternative solution to avoid boredom in learning English vocabulary. In addition, Kahoot itself allows teachers to build a fun and inventive learning process and actively involve students in classroom activities (Irwan et al., 2019). This finding is also supported by Hadijah et al. (2020) who reported that the Kahoot application tends to increase students' motivation, interest, and activeness in learning.

In this study, students also felt motivated to learn vocabulary, especially English. This aligns with previous research conducted by Wang et al. (2016) which stated that students were more motivated by Kahoot compared to clickers and paper quizzes. This finding was also discussed by Akdogan (2017) who said that teaching vocabulary using games can provide beneficial benefits because we not only learn knowledge but also have fun with this learning medium. Wright et al. (2005) also support the idea that games are often associated with fun. As we all know, students enjoy using Kahoot because they like to play games. In the current digital era, where technology supports and simplifies many aspects of life, many teachers incorporate computers and the internet into their classrooms. Even after the pandemic, teachers continue to use the internet as a learning tool. It has been proven that technology helps in teaching vocabulary (Ahmad et al., 2017). However, researchers found that there are still many teachers who lack knowledge about technology and prefer to provide material through books, which can make students bored and not interested in studying the material provided.

Researchers encountered several challenges when implementing Kahoot as a learning medium, one of which was inadequate school facilities. A reliable internet connection is essential for accessing the Kahoot game, but the school lacked internet network facilities such as Wi-Fi. Additionally, some students did not have data packages on their cell phones, raising concerns about their ability to access the game. However, researchers anticipated this issue and provided internet tethering from one device to another for those without data packages, ensuring all students could participate in the Kahoot game.

Using Kahoot has been shown to motivate students and enhance their vocabulary. The research results demonstrated a significant improvement in student performance: the mean pre-test score was 57.3, while the mean post-test score increased to 72.2 after incorporating Kahoot into the learning process. This indicates that interactive tools like Kahoot can effectively increase student participation in otherwise monotonous learning environments. Therefore, it can be concluded that Kahoot is a valuable alternative method for making English vocabulary classes more enjoyable and engaging.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the use of Kahoot game media in vocabulary learning conducted on Grade 7 students of SMP Negeri 7 Gorontalo, the researcher concluded that there was an impact on the students' abilities. This result can be seen from the results which show the difference between the mean scores of the students' pre-test and post-test. The mean score of the post-test is higher than the mean score of the pre-test. Thus, the use of the game Kahoot is effective in enriching students' vocabulary. Furthermore, this research can serve as a reference for teachers, encouraging them to be more creative in their teaching methods.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, K. S., Jocelyn, A., & Sudweeks, F. (2017). THE IMPACT OF UTILISING MOBILE ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING (MALL) ON VOCABULARY ACQUISITION AMONG MIGRANT WOMEN. *Interdisciplinary Journal of E-Skills and Lifelong Learning*, 13, 37–57. <https://www.informingscience.org/Publications/3703>
- Akdogan, E. (2017). DEVELOPING VOCABULARY IN GAME ACTIVITIES AND GAME MATERIALS. *Journal of Teaching and Education*, 7(1), 31–65. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED617641.pdf>
- Al-Manar, M, A. (2019). Reviewing Students' Vocabulary Mastery by Using Kahoot at Holmesglen Partnering with University Of Muhammadiyah Tangerang. *Acitya: Journal of Teaching & Education*, Vol. 1 (No. 2).
- Bicen, H., & Kocakoyun, S. (2018). Perceptions of Students for Gamification Approach : Kahoot as a Case Study. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 13(2), 72–93. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v13i02.7467>
- Dellos, R. (2015). Kahoot! A digital game resource for learning. *International Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning*, 12(4), 49–52. https://www.itdl.org/Journal/Apr_15/Apr15.pdf
- Flohr, S. (2010). Presenting and teaching vocabulary in the EFL classroom. GRIN Verlag. <http://www.grin.com>
- Hadijah, Pratolo, B. W., & Rondiyah. (2020). Interactive game “ Kahoot !” as the media of students' vocabulary assessment. *Journal on English as a Foreign Language (JEFL)*, 10(1), 87–105. <https://e-journal.iain-palangkaraya.ac.id/index.php/jefl/article/view/1670>
- Irwan, Luthfi, Z. F., & Waldi, A. (2019). Efektifitas Penggunaan Kahoot ! untuk Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar Siswa [Effectiveness of Using Kahoot ! to Improve Student Learning Outcomes]. *PEDAGOGIA: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.21070/pedagogia.v8i1.1866>
- Kadarwati, S., Sulistyarni, I., & Prayitno, E. (2021). Implementation of Gamification With Kahoot Platform! in Improving Student Learning Achievement UPBJJ UT Semarang. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal)*, 4(4), 10998–11003. <https://www.bircu-journal.com/index.php/birci/article/view/3156>
- Khoshsima, H., Saed, A., & Yazdani, A. (2015). Instructional Games and Vocabulary Enhancement : Case of Iranian Pre-Intermediate EFL Learners. *International Journal of Language and Linguistics*, 3(6), 328–332. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijll.20150306.12>
- Licorish, S. A., Owen, H., & Daniel, B. K. (2017). “ Go Kahoot !” Enriching Classroom Engagement , Motivation and Learning Experience with Games. *International Conference on Computers in Education*, December. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322150947_Go_Kahoot_Enriching_Classroom_Engagement_Motivation_and_Learning_Experience_with_Games
- Sugiyono. (2015). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan (Pendekatan kuantitatif, kualitatif, dan R&D)*. Bandung: Alfabeta CV.
- Thornbury, S. (2002). *How to Teach Vocabulary*. Pearson Education.
- Wang, A. I., Zhu, M., & Saetre, R. (2016). The Effect of Digitizing and Gamifying Quizzing in Classrooms. *European Conference on Game Based Learning (ECGBL)*, October. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/309292274_The_Effect_of_Digitizing_and_Gamifying_Quizzing_in_Classrooms
- Wright, A., Betteridge, D., & Buckby, M. (2005). *Games for Language Learning*. Cambridge University Press.